

Chemistry of Herbarumin I, Stagonolide A and Structurally Related Phytotoxic Ten-Membered Lactones: Oxidative Cleavage, Stereospecific Epoxidation, Transannulation and Dimerization

Anatoly Fedorov^{*‡}, Alena Alekseeva[†], Anna Dalinova[†], Daniil Kretov[§], Valentin Radiupov[‡], Anton Slukin[‡], Victor Khrustalev^{±¶}, Sergey Smirnov[‡], Alexander Sikalov[◇], Aleksandr Zaichenko^ℓ, Alexander Berestetskiy[†]

[‡]Independent researcher, Paris 75018, France

[†]All-Russian Institute of Plant Protection, Podbelskogo st., 3, Pushkin, St. Petersburg 196608, Russian Federation

[‡]St. Petersburg State University, Universitetsky Av. 26, St.Petersburg 198504, Russian Federation

[§]Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University, St.Petersburg 195251, Russian Federation

[±]Peoples' Friendship University of Russia (RUDN University), 6 Miklukho-Maklay Street, Moscow 117198, Russian Federation

[¶]N. D. Zelinsky Institute of Organic Chemistry of Russian Academy of Sciences, Leninsky Prospekt, 47, Moscow 119991, Russian Federation

^ℓAcademia Libera, Buffalo 14226, United States

[◇]University of Chicago, 929 E 57th St, Chicago 60637, United States

ABSTRACT

Ten-membered lactones (TMLs) produced by phytopathogenic fungi are considered as model compounds for the development of nature-inspired agrochemicals with novel mechanisms of action. Despite their structural simplicity, TMLs display a broad range of biological activities. Although total synthesis methods for many TMLs have been developed, systematic data on their chemical properties remain highly limited. To address this gap, we investigated the reactivity of herbarumin I, 2-*epi*-herbarumin II, stagonolides J-K, pinolidoxin and their C-7 oxidized analogs in oxidation, hydrogenation and isomerisation reactions. We demonstrate that their spatially constrained architecture and functional group topology promote distinctive and reproducible reactivity patterns, including stereospecific epoxidation at the C5–C6 bond, mild oxidative cleavage at C7–C8, Pd/Pt-catalyzed allylic transposition, transannulation to chromone derivatives, and base-induced dimerization into fused tetrahydrofuran scaffolds. As a result, 31 new compounds were synthesized, three new reactions were discovered with mechanistic insights provided, absolute configuration was established for stagonolide J and stagochromene A and revised for 5,6-epoxypinolidoxin. Preliminary conclusions were drawn on the chemical lability of unsaturated C7-keto derivatives of TMLs in protic media. Such mapping of structure–reactivity relationships within this TMLs subclass provides a foundation for future semisynthetic derivatization, chemical stability assessment, and rational expansion of biologically relevant scaffolds.

Ten-membered lactones (TMLs) produced by phytopathogenic fungi are considered as model compounds for the development of pesticides with new mechanisms of action. Despite their structural simplicity, compounds of this subclass have a wide and diverse range of biological activities. Today, more than 200 representatives of natural TMLs are known¹⁻⁴. For many of them, total synthesis methods have been developed⁵⁻⁶. Furthermore, methods for synthesizing small and medium-sized lactones are constantly improving⁷⁻⁹.

Nevertheless, the biotechnological source of TMLs production remains significant. Some phytopathogenic fungi are able to produce compounds of this group with high titres¹⁰. The biotechnological availability of TMLs allows for the development of methods to chemically modify them, aimed at increasing their target activity and creating new nature-inspired agrochemicals or pharmaceuticals. For instance, semisynthetic mono- and bis(acetyl)derivatives of herbarumin I exhibited potent seedling growth inhibition activity (ID_{50} 0.04-0.07 $\mu\text{mole/seed}$) compared to natural non-acetylated analogue¹¹.

The synthesis of new TMLs also allows replenishing the library of known natural and semi-synthetic compounds for the search of structure-biological activity relationships. For example, in our latest works, it was shown that derivatives with an α,β -unsaturated keto group possess acute non-target toxicity in a wide range of bioassays¹¹⁻¹². In certain cases, it may be advantageous to semi-synthetically produce biologically active natural TMLs with lower titers from more readily available analogs.

Among modern approaches for the development of new agrochemicals, the intermediate derivatization approach is used, including the active compound derivatization method¹³, which is also suitable for natural compounds. A significant obstacle to the application of this method to fungal TMLs is the lack of systematic information regarding their chemical properties.

Based on the structure of TMLs, reactions typical for esters are expected, leading to opening of the lactone ring under the influence of nucleophilic reagents or strong reducing agents¹⁴, as well as ring-opening polymerizations¹⁵. Rare examples of functionalized lactone rearrangements involving double and triple carbon-carbon bonds represent ring contraction and expansion reactions¹⁶⁻¹⁹.

The literature contains numerous examples of semisynthetic derivatives of herbarumins I and II²⁰⁻²³, pinolidoxin²⁴, putaminoxin²⁵, stagonolide E and curvulide A^{12, 26}, truncatenolide²⁷. However, the reactions used to obtain these derivatives aren't usually systematized and are aimed primarily at structure elucidation⁵⁻⁶ or establishing structure-biological activity relationship^{11-12, 28-29}. Moreover, they are not designed to reveal the impact of oxygen-containing substituents on the reactivity of these TMLs. Currently, only one work covers non-enzymatic reactions of fungal TMLs from the decarestrictine family³⁰, whereas Lu et al. investigated the retro-aza-Michael transformations of saccharothriolides B and L³¹⁻³². Thus, a broader chemical understanding of these natural products is still lacking. To address this gap, and to explore unique chemistry of TMLs, we carried out a systematic analysis of the reactivity of nine TMLs bearing similar structural motifs at C-5–C-8 under oxidation, hydrogenation and isomerisation reactions. Given the extensive experimental scope and emphasis on chemical reactivity, bioactivity assessment of

newly synthesized compounds was intentionally omitted for clarity and to maintain a consistent structural and mechanistic perspective on TMLs' unique chemistry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Six known TMLs (**1-6**) were used as starting compounds: herbarumin I (**1**), stagonolides A (**2**), J (**3**) and K (**4**)^{10, 33-34}, pinolidoxin (**5**) and 2-*epi*-herbarumin II (**6**)³⁵⁻³⁶. Their structural similarities include the presence of a 5E double C=C bond, an *n*-propyl moiety at position C-9, and at least one OH group at C-7 and/or C-8. Among the differences, one can note the presence of substituents at C-2, a mismatch in the stereoconfiguration of atoms C-7 and C-9, as well as a conjugated keto group at position C-7 in stagonolide A (**2**). In order to add more keto derivatives into the existing set of starting substances, we obtained three C-7 oxidized semisynthetic analogues of lactones **4-6** (see below). Additionally, we have developed a semi-synthetic method for obtaining 2-*epi*-herbarumin II (**6**) with a yield of 77% based on more accessible pinolidoxin **5** (see experimental section).

Allylic OH oxidation vs C-C cleavage

Biotechnological accessibility of stagonolide A (**2**) was inferior to its closest analog herbarumin I (**1**). Hence C-7 oxidation of the lactone **1** using manganese dioxide employed by Srihari and Prabhakar et al. in total synthesis of compound **2**, seemed optimal^{22-23, 37}. Manganese dioxide is a mild oxidant, however its reactivity is often sensitive to stereoconfiguration of the oxidized alcohols, while the reaction reproducibility depends on preparation method³⁸. It's known to easily oxidize vicinal diols to dicarbonyl compounds via C-C cleavage³⁹. Herbarumin I (**1**) possesses both allylic hydroxyl and glycol moieties, therefore low chemoselectivity was expected from manganese oxidants. Our experiments with lactone **1** and manganese dioxide ended up with two products - desired stagonolide A (**2**) and dialdehyde **7**. Average isolated yields of compound **2** and **7** were 34 and 54% respectively (figure 1). Manganese dioxide prepared by the Attenborough method³⁸ oxidized herbarumin I similarly to the commercial one.

They both provided total conversion of the starting material. NMR yield measurements revealed an even larger amount of dialdehyde **7** being formed with activated MnO₂ (8% of **2** against 65% of **7**). By-product **7** was not previously described by Srihari and Prabhakar et al. despite the fact they used the same oxidation method.

The second reagent of choice was barium manganate. Similarly to activated manganese dioxide, it's a mild and easily prepared oxidant suitable for allylic alcohol oxidation and has a better reputation in terms of chemoselectivity^{38, 40}. However, oxidation of herbarumin I (**1**) with barium manganate afforded the same mixture of desired ketone **2** and the C-C cleavage product **7** with isolated yields of 17 and 69% respectively. Therefore, expected chemoselectivity has not been achieved using manganese based oxidants.

Another disadvantage of these oxidation methods concerned reverse-phase HPLC purification of the final product. Dialdehyde **7** possesses an unusual wide L-shaped chromatographic peak that inevitably overlaps with stagonolide A (**2**) peak during the separation process and contaminates it (see supplementary materials). To overcome this issue, column chromatography on silica could be used because normal phase chromatography provides greater resolution for the mixture of **2** and **7**.

The C-7 epimer of lactone **1**, named stagonolide J (**3**), quantitatively undergoes C-C cleavage into dialdehyde **7** with manganese-based oxidants with the isolated yields of 81-96%. No traces of desired stagonolide A were found during TLC and NMR investigation of the reaction mixture (figure 1).

Figure 1. Mild oxidation of compounds **1,3-6** to carbonyl compounds. Reagents and conditions: (i) 3 equiv. of DDQ, dioxane, 60°C; (ii) 20 equiv. of MnO₂, CH₂Cl₂, rt; (iii) 10 equiv. of BaMnO₄, CH₂Cl₂, rt

However, the side product **7** has its own relevance. If both lactones are cleaved into identical dialdehyde **7**, then they both possess R configuration of C-9 chiral center. Unlike herbarumin I (**1**), only relative configuration for stagonolide J (**3**) was assigned previously **33** using NOESY NMR correlation profile. Our data add chemical evidence of the stereodescriptors set for lactone **3**. Hence, stagonolide J (**3**) absolute configuration is *5E, 7R, 8S, 9R*. X-Ray analysis of its diacetylated analog described below further corroborated this statement. To the best of our knowledge, the formation of dialdehyde **7** from lactones **1** and **3** is the first evidence of glycol cleavage caused by barium manganate.

Significant progress in semisynthetic stagonolide A (**2**) preparation was achieved using 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyanobenzo-1,4-quinone (DDQ) as an oxidant. Despite a multi-step purification, the isolated yield of the desired product rose up to 90% while no dialdehyde **7** was formed during the reaction. However, high conversion of starting material requires heating as opposed to the experiments with manganese-based oxidants. The method was scaled up to 0.8 gram of initial lactone **1** loading and was further used for stagonolide A semisynthetic preparation.

Although herbarumin I (**1**) responded well to DDQ oxidation, its C-7 epimer appeared to be unreactive. Thus, no reaction occurred with stagonolide J (**3**) even after prolonged exposure. This result strongly highlights sensitivity of the oxidants towards the C-7 stereoconfiguration of these TMLs.

Pinolidoxin **5** was initially tested in reaction with DDQ. However, no desired product was isolated as a result. Decomposition of the reaction components was suspected after TLC examination of the mixture after 20 h of reaction. HPLC purification also failed to separate product **8** from the resulting multi component mixture. In contrast to DDQ, manganese dioxide afforded desired C-7 oxidized pinolidoxin analog **8** with 38% isolated yield. Similarly to herbarumin I (**1**), oxidation of pinolidoxin **5** by manganese dioxide is accompanied by C-C cleavage by-product **9**. The isolation yield of dialdehyde **9** was 46%. Inevitable overlapping of peaks on C18RP chromatogram makes reversed phase separation of compounds **8** and **9** ineffective. Proper separation was achieved using column chromatography on silica. Detailed NMR data of dialdehydes **7** and **9** are presented in the supplementary materials.

Compound **8** we refer to as pinolidoxone was previously unknown. However, Wang et al. proposed it as an intermediate product in biosynthesis of bellidisin A ⁴¹.

Analytical HPLC was used to compare both oxidation methods quantitatively (figure 2). The plots show that both methods provide almost total conversion of pinolidoxin **5** after 1 day, although manganese dioxide consumes most of the starting material after a few hours. Meanwhile, the reaction with DDQ demonstrates slower consumption of **5** and the concentration of pinolidoxone **8** doesn't increase after several hours. The rise of control sample concentration represents solvent loss due to evaporation. Thus the actual concentration of the desired ketone **8** drops down over time in the experiments with DDQ. It indicates undesirable chemical reactions taking place as well as lability of pinolidoxin **5** and pinolidoxone **8** at such conditions. Consequently, despite the low yield and formation of by-product **9**, manganese dioxide emerged as the preferable oxidant for pinolidoxin **5** compared to DDQ.

Figure 2. Quantitative HPLC evaluation of **5** oxidation progress: (A) using MnO₂ as oxidant; (B) using DDQ as oxidant

2-epi-Herbarumin II (**6**) responded differently to manganese dioxide oxidation compared to **1** and **5**. Only trace amounts of dicarbonyl compounds were observed after NMR examination of the reaction mixture. And unlike compounds **1** and **5**, *2-epi*-herbarumin II (**6**) was not completely consumed during the reaction. Due to poor solubility of lactone **6** in dichloromethane, the reaction was carried out in ethyl acetate. The resulting oxidation product (2*S*)-2-hydroxystagonolide A (**10**) was formed with 37 % yield measured by NMR spectroscopy and isolated with 32% yield using column chromatography. The higher selectivity of lactone **6** oxidation does not appear to be solvent-dependent. This is evidenced by substantial amounts of the dicarbonyl by-products formed during the oxidation of lactones **1** and **5** with manganese dioxide in ethyl acetate solution.

Lactones **8** and **10** are semisynthetic C-2 substituted analogs of stagonolide A (**2**). HRESIMS data confirmed their the molecular formula as follows: C₁₈H₂₄O₆ for compound **8** (359.1460 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd for C₁₈H₂₄O₆Na, 359.1465)) and C₁₂H₁₈O₅ for compound **10** (265.1048 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd for C₁₂H₁₈O₅Na, 265.1046)). 2D NMR analysis of compound **8** reveals three spin systems: sorbic acid residue (C-2' at δ 117.7 ppm, C-3' at δ 146.4, C-4' at δ 129.6, C-5' at δ 141.4, C-6' at δ 18.8), C-2–C-5 fragment (C-2 at δ 69.0, C-3 at δ 30.2, C-4 at δ 27.5, C-5 at δ 140.8) and C-8–C-12 fragment (C-8 at δ 76.2, C-9 at δ 75.2, C-10 at δ 34.1, C-11 at δ 17.7, C-12 at δ 13.7). These spin systems are split by the carboxyl carbon C-1 at δ 170.5, the carbonyl carbon C-7 at δ 199.4 within the lactone ring, and the carboxyl carbon C-1' at δ 165.8 of the sorbic acid residue. 2D NMR analysis of compound **10** demonstrates that the lactone ring has two spin systems (C-2 at δ 69.2, C-3 at δ 31.7, C-4 at δ 26.4, C-5 at δ 143.1 along with C-8 at δ 76.2, C-9 at δ 75.6, C-10 at δ 34.1, C-11 at δ 18.2, C-12 at δ 13.6) split by the carboxyl carbon C-1 at δ 172.7 and the carbonyl carbon C-7 at δ 199.4. Pinolidoxone **8** and 2-hydroxystagonolide A (**10**) inherited all C=C bonds from corresponding precursors **5-6**, while stereoconfiguration of the substituents at C-8 and C-9 remained intact as a result of the oxidation. Hence, compounds **8** and **10** have 2*S*, 5*E*, 7*S*, 9*R* absolute configurations. For both compounds NOESY correlations were observed between H-6 (δ 6.51 for

compound **8** and δ 6.55 for compound **10**) and H-8 (δ 4.07 for compound **8** and δ 4.12 for compound **10**), which indicates the *cis*-arrangement of these protons (table 1, figure 3).

Table 1. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data of compounds **8** and **10** in CDCl_3 (400 and 100 MHz, respectively)

position	Compound 8		Compound 10	
	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)
1	170.5, C	-	172.7, C	-
2	69.0, CH	5.41, d (4.5)	69.2, CH	4.47, dd (4.1, 2.8)
3	30.2, CH ₂	2.37, 2.20, m	31.7, CH ₂	2.21, m
4	27.5, CH ₂	2.52, 2.34, m	26.4, CH ₂	2.62, 2.25, m
5	140.8, CH	6.27*, m	143.1, CH	6.31, ddd (15.9, 11.3, 4.5)
6	133.3, CH	6.51, d (15.8)	132.7, CH	6.55, d (15,9)
7	199.4, C	-	199.4, C	-
8	76.2, CH	4.07, d (9.6)	76.2, CH	4.12, dd (9.7, 6.2)
9	75.2, CH	4.69, t (9.5)	75.6, CH	4.75, td (9.6, 2.4)
10	34.1, CH ₂	1.93*, 1.63, m	34.1, CH ₂	2.06, 1.76, m
11	17.7, CH ₂	1.40, 1.26, m	18.2, CH ₂	1.45, 1.36, m
12	13.7, CH ₃	0.90, t (7.4)	13.6, CH ₃	0.96, t (7.4)
1'	165.8, C	-	-	-
2'	117.7, CH	5.94, d (15.4)	-	-
3'	146.4, CH	7.38, dd (15.4, 9.8)	-	-
4'	129.6, CH	6.26*, m	-	-
5'	141.4, CH	6.30*, m	-	-
6'	18.8, CH ₃	1.92, d (5.1)	-	-
OH (2)	-	-	-	2.48, bs
OH (8)	-	3.60, bs	-	3.64, d (6.3)

*signals partially obscured

Figure 3. Key 2D NMR correlations of pinolidoxone **8** and 2S-hydroxystagonolide A (**10**)

2-*epi*-Herbarumin II (**6**) oxidation with DDQ was not as effective as in case of herbarumin I (**1**). More than half of the starting material remained intact according to TLC and HPLC examination of reaction mixture. Hence, manganese dioxide seems to be preferable compared to DDQ due to easier work-up procedure and similar chemoselectivity.

Resilience to the mild oxidants was also observed for stagonolide K (**4**). Our previous work¹¹ showed that manganese containing oxidants afford scarce yields of C7-oxidized analogue (**11**). The attempt to oxidize lactone **4** with DDQ in this work afforded only trace amounts of ketone **11** (as detected by NMR).

Thus DDQ was effective only against herbarumin I (**1**), while inorganic oxidants remain preferable for compounds' **8**, **10-11** preparation. The examples listed above illustrate unexpected differences in the oxidation chemoselectivity of lactones **1-6** depending on C-2, C-8 substituents, and C-7 stereoconfiguration.

Stereospecific Prilezhaev epoxidation

Previous evidence of stagonolide E stereoselective epoxidation via both Prilezhaev and Sharpless methods^{12, 26} highlights the importance of steric factors for unsaturated TML ring. Underestimation of these factors may lead to unreliable assignment of stereodescriptors for natural and synthetic TMLs and misleading SAR data as a consequence. Initially, we tested lactones **1-4** and their acetylated derivatives **12-14** in reaction with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in dichloromethane solution. As a result, the epoxides **5-20** were afforded with moderate to high yields of 50-80%, and only bis(acetyl)stagonolide J (**13**) appeared to be unreactive under these conditions. Subsequently, 5,6-epoxy-bis(acetyl)stagonolide J (**19**) was obtained via acetylation of **16** (figure 4). Complete stereoselectivity was observed as only one diastereomer was formed in each case according to NMR and HPLC data. Acetylated herbarumin I (**12**) and stagonolides J (**13**), K (**14**) played an important role in elucidating the cause for such selectivity. At first, H-bond orienting, or Henbest effect⁴², was suggested as an explanation. However, an alternative synthetic route to the acetylated epoxides **18**, **20** demonstrated no link between OH group accessibility and stereoselectivity of epoxidation. The unsuccessful attempt to turn bis(acetyl)stagonolide J (**13**) into the corresponding epoxide **19** demonstrates that steric factors have strong influence on reactivity of these TMLs with *m*CPBA. In addition, X-Ray diffraction data were obtained for acetates **12** and **13** using MoK α and CuK α radiation correspondingly (figure 5). The resulting ORTEP diagram of **13** supports the accuracy of stagonolide J (**3**) absolute configuration assignment based on oxidative cleavage reactions (see above, figure 1).

Figure 4. Synthesis of compounds **18-20** via two synthetic routes. Reagents and conditions: (i) 1.4 equiv of *m*CPBA, CH₂Cl₂; (ii) 20-60 equiv of Ac₂O, pyridine, rt

Figure 5. ORTEP diagrams of bis(acetyl)herbarumin I (**12**), bis(acetyl)stagonolide J (**13**), 5,6-epoxyherbarumin I (**15**), 5,6-epoxy-2-*epi*-herbarumin II (**21**)

Acetylation of lactones **16-17** also provided better signal resolution of the protons attached to the epoxy ring (C-5, C-6 positions) in the NMR spectra of the resulting esters **19-20**. It allowed us to distinguish the corresponding cross peaks in the NOE spectra and measure spin-spin coupling constants. The opposite outcome was observed in case of acetylation of epoxyherbarumin I (**15**) (figure 6).

Figure 6. The difference in signal resolution of H-5 and H-6 protons in ¹H NMR spectrum between epoxydes **15-17** and their acetylated analogs **18-20**

Thus, NOE correlation patterns of each epoxide were analyzed and compared to establish spatial arrangement of the epoxy ring. Additionally, 2-*epi*-herbarumin II (**21**), 5,6-epoxypinolidoxin **22**, and pinolidoxin diepoxides **23a,b** were obtained by the same epoxidation method with isolated yields of 95, 61 and 29% respectively. Due to structural similarity, their spectra displayed a similar correlation pattern observed for compound **15** (figures 7-8).

Figure 7. (A) Prilezhaev epoxidation of 2-*epi*-herbarumin II (**6**) and pinolidoxin **5**. Structure of bellidisin D (**24**). (B) Quantitative HPLC evaluation of lactone **5** epoxidation progress using *m*CPBA as oxidant

Spatial proximity of the protons H-6 and H-8 is evidenced by the corresponding NOE cross-peaks for compounds **15**, **19**, **21-22**, and **23a,b**. On the contrary, the protons H-5 and H-7 of these epoxides are apparently *trans*-arranged and do not show pronounced correlations. However, in case of diacetyloxystagonolide J (**19**) the H-5–H-7 correlation occurs due to the inverted configuration of C-7 chiral center. Acetyloxystagonolide K (**20**) possesses *cis*-arranged H-5 and H-7 protons as well, indicating that the plane of C-4–C-7 region of this molecule is flipped by 180 degrees compared to other epoxides in the set. The correlations between H-5/H-9, H-5/H-7, and H-7/H-9 in the spectrum of compound **20** supports this hypothesis. Diastereomeric mixture of pinolidoxin diepoxides **23a,b** additionally possesses the correlation between the protons H-4'/H-6' of the side chain (figure 8).

Figure 8. Key 2D NOESY NMR correlations of compounds **15,19-23a,b**

X-Ray analysis of compounds **15** and **21** reveals that the C-4–C-7 region of the molecules is flattened and arranged parallel to the plane of the ester group (figure 5). Meanwhile, the oxirane ring is placed at the peripheral side of the C-4–C-7 region. It gives rise to a very specific and predictable spatial arrangement of the hydrogen atoms reflected in the corresponding correlations described above. It was especially useful for stereoconfiguration assignment of C-5 and C-6 atoms in the epoxides presented here, particularly, for closely related molecules such as **18** and **22-23a,b**.

Analysis of the ^1H NMR spectra of the synthesized epoxides also provides a coherent conformational picture. The measured J values for H-5–H-6 coupling are approximately 1.8-2.2 Hz for each epoxide that is exemplary for *trans*-epoxides⁴³. As expected, J values for H-6–H-7 coupling are 8.7-8.8 Hz in the spectra of compounds **19-20** (obtained from stagonolides J-K) due to *trans*-disposition of the corresponding protons. Simultaneously, J (H-6–H-7) values of lactones **15,18**, and **21-23a,b** (originated from herbarumin I, 2-*epi*-herbarumin II and pinolidoxin) are close to zero certifying the torsion angles around 80 degrees, which is also confirmed by X-Ray data obtained for **15** and **21**.

Considering the absolute configuration of stagonolide J (discussed above), herbarumin I²¹, stagonolide K³⁴, 2-*epi*-herbarumin II, and pinolidoxin^{20,35} along with conformation of their epoxy derivatives **15-23a,b**, it seems highly plausible that the exclusive stereoselectivity of Prilezhaev epoxidation is simply caused by the geometry of the C-4–C-7 linkage of the initial lactones **1,3-6,12,14**. Like in the previously explained case of stagonolide E epoxidation¹², the olefinic plane is perpendicular to the plane of the lactone ring; thus, only less-hindered peripheral side of the double bond could be attacked by the oxidant. Resilience of bis(acetyl)stagonolide J (**13**) against *m*CPBA is apparently caused by additional spatial shielding of the double bond with an 7-O-acetyl moiety (figure 9).

Figure 9. Steric shielding of C-5–C-6 double bond in TMLs directing the attack of *m*CPBA molecule

Thus, the combination of spectroscopic, crystallographic, and chemical data allows us to assign the following absolute configuration to the synthesized epoxides: 5R,6R,7R,8S,9R for **15**, 5R,6R,7S,8S,9R for **16**, 5S,6S,7R,9S for **17**, 5R,6S,7S,8R,9R for **18**, 5R,6S,7R,8R,9R for **19**, 5S,6R,7R,9S for **20**, 2S,5R,6R,7R,8S,9R for **21**, 2S,5R,6R,7R,8S,9R for **22**, and 2S,4'R/S,5'R/S,5R,6R,7R,8S,9R for **23a,b**.

5,6-Epoxy-pinolidoxin **22** is one of the rare examples of 5,6-epoxides isolated from a natural source^{41,44}. The absolute configuration assignment for C-5 and C-6 chiral carbons made by Wang et al.⁴¹ was based only on the low-intensity H-5–H-9 cross-peak in the NOESY NMR spectra. In addition, the authors ignored the pronounced H-6–H-8 correlation (figure 8) that was present in the spectrum they provided as well as in our spectrum. Furthermore, the compounds **15** and **21**, that are considered as the closest structural analogs of epoxy-pinolidoxin **22**, also demonstrate weak H-5–H-9 correlations, but definitely have X-Ray confirmed 5R, 6R configurations. For that reason, the assignment made by Wang et al. for 5,6-epoxy-pinolidoxin **22** is unlikely to be correct due to misinterpretations of the spectroscopic data. Additionally, the authors overlooked the misinterpretation of the proton spectrum of compound **22** previously made by Evidente et al.⁴⁴. The corrected version of the NMR signals description for the epoxide **22** is presented in the supplementary file.

Along with 5,6-epoxy-pinolidoxin **22**, Wang et al. isolated its regioisomer called bellidisin D (**24**) with an epoxy ring located at sorbic acid residue (figure 7). Since pinolidoxin contains olefinic moieties at both lactone cycle and at the C-2 substituent chain, it was presumed that compound **24** might be one of the Prilezhaev epoxidation products. However, the by-products of reaction between **5** and *m*CPBA were di-epoxides **23a,b**. The isolated yields of **22** and **23a,b** are 61 and 29% respectively. Compounds **23a,b** appear to be a mixture of two diastereomers in 1:1 ratio and were not separated during HPLC purification. The formation of diastereomeric mixture **23a,b** was expected as no stereo control factors are present for

the C-2 side chain of the pinolidoxin **5** molecule. Meanwhile, the endocyclic double carbon-carbon bond was epoxidized to afford an epoxy ring with 5R,6R configurations in both isomers. HRESIMS data confirmed their molecular formula as follows: $C_{18}H_{26}O_8$ ($393.1523 [M + Na]^+$ (calcd for $C_{18}H_{26}O_8Na$, 393.1520)). The 1H NMR spectrum shows no signs of the mixture of products and contains four distinctive signals of each epoxy ring protons at δ 2.86 (t, $J = 2.5$ Hz, H-6), 2.98-3.05 (qu d, $J = 5.0, 2.0$ Hz, H-5'), 3.08 (d, $J = 10.5$ Hz, H-5) and 3.24 (d, $J = 6.7$ Hz, H-4'). However, the ^{13}C NMR spectrum exposes structural differences between the stereoisomers **23a,b**. Doubling of signals of the epoxidated sorbic acid moiety takes place at δ 17.51 and 17.53 (C-6'), 57.01 and 57.05 (C-4'), 57.75 and 57.85 (C-5'), 122.21 and 122.34 (C-2'), 146.13 and 146.17 (C-3'); as well as at δ 71.86 and 71.90 (C-8), 70.36 and 70.38 (C-2) of the carbons within the lactone ring. Meanwhile the carbon atoms of the endocyclic epoxy ring are presented by single peaks at δ 53.00 (C-5), 61.47 (C-6).

Quantitative HPLC investigation of the reaction demonstrated instant conversion of pinolidoxin **5** into 5,6-epoxide **22** while significantly smaller amounts of by-products **23a,b** were formed during the first hour. Further consumption of the monoepoxide and formation of diastereomeric diepoxides **23a,b** is supposedly caused by the excess of unreacted *m*CPBA (figure 7).

Another attempt to synthesize bellidisin D (**24**) via epoxidation of pinolidoxone **8** followed by reduction of C-7 carbonyl group was unsuccessful as well. Instead of sorbic acid residue, the C-7 and C-8 carbons were oxidized. The resulting dicarboxylic acid **25** was formed and isolated with a 40% yield, and no signals of compound **24** were found during NMR examination of the reaction mixture. The presumed mechanism apparently consists of Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of pinolidoxone **8** resulting in the 11-membered labile hemiacetal lactone followed by its spontaneous cleavage and then, the second iteration of Bayer-Villiger oxidation (figure 10). This is another example of mild oxidative carbon-carbon bond cleavage of TMLs listed in this work (see above).

Figure 10. Oxidative cleavage of pinolidoxone **8** with *m*CPBA

Consequently, the conformational features of herbarumin I (**1**) and its structural analogs dictate the conditions under which the Prilezhaev reaction proceeds stereospecifically at carbons C5–C6 using a non-selective reagent like mCPBA. This knowledge facilitates the prediction or, if necessary, revision of the absolute configuration of the chiral carbon atoms of the resulting epoxides with significant precision.

Allylic transposition vs transannulation

Previously, we demonstrated that Pd/C-catalyzed hydrogenation of stagonolide E affords the by-product with a carbonyl group and saturated carbon-carbon bonds¹². This reaction is known as the transposition of allylic alcohols and occurs in the presence of transition metals and their complexes⁴⁵.

Hydrogenation of the compounds **1-6**, **8**, **10**, **12** revealed their tendency to form isomerization products. Stagonolide A (**2**) is predictively converted into dihydrostagonolide A (**26**) using Pd/C activated by hydrogen. Unexpectedly, the same compound **26** was obtained via transposition of herbarumin I (**1**) under both Pd and Pt catalysis. Consequently, a one-pot two-step procedure with sodium borohydride addition was employed for the preparation of dihydroherbarumin I (**27**) (figure 11). The reduction of the carbonyl group of dihydrostagonolide A (**26**) with sodium borohydride proceeds stereospecifically to 7S derivatives similar to the previously described reduction of stagonolide A (**2**)⁴⁶. This was established by the significant difference between the NMR spectra of compound **27** (3.88, 1H, dd, $J = 7.5, 3.2$ Hz, H-8) and its C-7 epimer - dihydrostagonolide J (**28**) (3.50, 1H, t, $J = 8.9$ Hz, H-8).

Stagonolide J (**3**) on the contrary, did not afford isomerisation product **26** in reaction with palladium hydride and underwent conventional hydrogenation route forming dihydrostagonolide J (**28**). Stagonolide K (**4**) was also quantitatively transformed into the corresponding dihydrostagonolide K (**29**) under these conditions, isolated as a mixture of two conformers in a 5:1 ratio. As noted earlier, lactones **3** and **4** possess a *trans*-disposition of the protons at C-6 and C-7 unlike herbarumin I (**1**), 2-*epi*-herbarumin II (**6**), and pinolidoxin **5**. This spatial arrangement of atoms likely disfavours the carbonyl group formation via metal hydride elimination^{45, 47}, thereby preventing transposition. Isomerization also didn't proceed for the acetylated lactone **12**, which was converted to bis(acetyl)dihydroherbarumin I (**30**) under identical conditions (figure 11).

Figure 11. Difference in chemoselectivity of compounds **1-4** and **12** towards Pd/Pt catalyzed hydrogenation. Reagents and conditions: (i) Pd/C or Pt/C, H₂ atm, THF, rt; (ii) 1.2 equiv of NaBH₄, EtOH, rt. The isolated yields of compound **26** are listed for one-stage reduction. The two-step process was executed without isolation of the intermediate products

Similar to compounds **1** and **2**, both pinolidoxin **5** and its C-7 oxidized analogue pinolidoxone **8** afforded the identical mixture of products. The major one is the saturated lactone **31** resulting from simultaneous allylic transposition of the endocyclic double bond and hydrogenation of the sorbic acid residue. The minor product **32** is presumably formed by two synchronous hydrogen addition and transannulation. The NMR-measured ratio between isomers **31** and **32** varied and was estimated as 7:3 with the isolated yields of 55 and 14% respectively. Replacing the palladium catalyst with platinum showed no difference in chemoselectivity of the reaction.

Subsequent one pot reduction of the compounds **5** or **8** with hydrogen followed by sodium borohydride addition yielded the saturated lactone **33** and the chromone **34** isolated with 18 and 25% yields respectively. Unlike ordinary Pd-catalyzed reduction, this two-step reaction was performed in ethanol and provided higher yield of the chromone by-product **34** that originated from compound **32**. The latter was not isolated during one pot process. Hexahydropinolidoxin **33** was previously prepared by single-stage hydrogenation of pinolidoxin **5** in the presence of Adams' catalyst by Evidente et al.²⁴, and surprisingly no isomerization products were reported by the authors.

2-*epi*-Herbarumin II (**6**) and its C-7 oxidized analogue 2-hydroxystagonolide A **10** in the presence of activated Pd underwent similar transposition and transannulation, yielding products **35** and **36** in 4:1 ratio (measured by NMR), isolated with 27 and 16% yields respectively (figure 12).

Figure 12. Difference in chemoselectivity of compounds 5-6,8,10 and 38 towards Pd/Pt catalyzed hydrogenation. Preparation of pinolidoxin acetates 37-38. Reagents and conditions: (i) Pd/C or Pt/C, H₂ atm, THF, rt; (ii) 1.2 equiv of NaBH₄, EtOH, rt; (iii) 2 equiv (for preparation of 37) or 60 equiv (for preparation of 38) of Ac₂O, pyridine, rt. The isolated yields of compounds 31-32 are listed for one-stage reduction. The two-step process was executed without isolation of the intermediate products

By-products 32 and 36 represent rare examples of substituted octahydrochromene-4-ones with a hemiketal moiety at C-8a position. Their structural analog bellidisin A was previously isolated from *Phoma bellidis* culture by Wang et. al.⁴¹. The authors proposed a biosynthetic route to the chromone core via *oxa*-Michael addition of water to the electron deficient C-5–C-6 double bond of pinolidoxone 8 accompanied by intramolecular Claisen condensation followed by 5-O-methylation. The absolute configuration of bellidisin A was determined using ECD spectroscopy, thus enabling a relevant structural comparison with chromones 32 and 36.

HRESIMS data confirmed their molecular formulae as follows: C₁₈H₃₀O₆ for compound 32 (365.1934 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd for C₁₈H₃₀O₆Na, 365.1935)) and C₁₂H₂₀O₅ for compound 36 (267.1202 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd for C₁₂H₂₀O₅Na, 267.1203)). 2D NMR analysis of compound 32 revealed three spin systems: caproic acid residue (C-2' at δ 34.6, C-3' at δ 24.9, C-4' at δ 31.2, C-5' at δ 22.3, C-6' at δ 14.0), the C-4a–C-8 fragment (C-4a at δ 50.5, C-5 at δ 20.6, C-6 at δ 18.7, C-7 at δ 27.3, C-8 at δ 72.3), and the C-2–C-3 fragment attached to the C-9–C-11 propyl group (C-2 at δ 76.4, C-3 at δ 76.6, C-9 at δ 35.0, C-10 at δ 18.2, C-11 at δ 13.9). The key HMBC correlations are observed for H-4a/C-4, OH-3/C-4, H-4a/C-8a, H-5/C-8a, H-8/C-8a, H-8/C-1', H-2'/C-1', and H-8/C-4. Hence, these spin systems are connected by the hemiketal carbon C-8a at δ 99.0, the carbonyl carbon C-4 at δ 207.4 within the chromone core, and the carboxyl carbon C-1' of the caproic acid residue at δ 172.8. Similarly to bellidisin A, the proton H-4a of

chromone **32** has an axial arrangement, as shown by the axial-axial coupling constant in the ^1H NMR spectrum. Both chromones have an almost identical triplet corresponding to the proton H-8 at δ 5.02 ($J = 2.9$ Hz)⁴¹ and possess the NOESY correlations between H-3 and H-4a as well as between H-6 and H-4a. Chromone **32** also has H-8/OH-8a correlation (figure 13, table 2).

2D NMR analysis of compound **36** reveals two spin systems within the chromone core: the C-4a–C-8 fragment (C-4a at δ 49.7, C-5 at δ 20.7, C-6 at δ 18.1, C-7 at δ 28.0, C-8 at δ 72.7) and the C-2–C-3 fragment attached to the C-9–C-11 propyl group (C-2 at δ 77.0, C-3 at δ 76.4, C-9 at δ 35.1, C-10 at δ 18.5, C-11 at δ 14.0). The key HMBC correlations were observed for H-4a/C-4, OH-3/C-4, H-3/C-4, H-2/C-4, H-4a/C-8a, H-5/C-8a, H-8/C-8a, and H-8/C-4. Hence, these spin-spin systems are connected by the hemiketal carbon C-8a at δ 100.7 and the carbonyl carbon C-4 at δ 207.7. Similarly to bellidisin A and compound **32**, the proton H-4a of chromone **36** has an axial arrangement, as shown by the axial-axial coupling constant in the ^1H NMR spectrum. The proton H-8 with equatorial arrangement is presented by the corresponding triplet ($J = 2.8$ Hz) at δ 3.70. Similarly to bellidisin A and chromone **32**, compound **36** possesses the NOESY correlations between H-3 and H-4a as well as between H-6 and H-4a (figure 13, table 2).

Reduction of chromone **32** with sodium borohydride afforded the *cis*-glycol **34** with a molecular formula $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_6$ (367.2089 $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ (calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$, 367.2091)). 2D NMR analysis reveals two spin systems: the octahydrochromene carbon chain (C-2 at δ 68.7, C-3 at δ 71.5, C-4 at δ 72.5, C-4a at δ 40.0, C-5 at δ 25.2, C-6 at δ 19.9, C-7 at δ 27.7, C-8 at δ 71.9, C-9 at δ 33.9, C-10 at δ 18.1, C-11 at δ 13.9) and the caproic acid residue (C-2' at δ 34.7, C-3' at δ 24.8, C-4' at δ 31.2, C-5' at δ 22.3, C-6' at δ 14.2). The key HMBC correlations were observed for H-2/C-8a, H-4/C-8a, H-4a/C-8a, H-5/C-8a, H-8/C-8a, H-8/C-4a, H-8/C-1', H-2'/C-1'. The key NOE correlations were observed for H-2/OH-4, H-3/H-4a, and H-4/OH-3. The proton H-8 with equatorial arrangement appears as the triplet ($J = 2.8$ Hz) at δ 4.87. Equatorial arrangement of the proton H-4 at δ 3.93 was deduced by spin-spin coupling constant value of the neighbouring axially arranged proton H-3 ($J = 3.3$ Hz) at δ 3.30 (Figure 13, table 2).

2-*epi*-Herbarumin II (**6**) and its C-7 oxidized analogue 2-hydroxystagonolide A **10** in the presence of activated Pd underwent similar transposition and transannulation, yielding products **35** and **36** in 4:1 ratio (measured by NMR), isolated with 27 and 16% yields respectively (figure 12).

Figure 13. Key 2D NMR correlations of compounds **32**, **34** and **36**

Tandem addition-transannulation proposed by Wang et al. also explains formation of chromones **32** and **36** in the presence of activated transition metals. The proposed reaction mechanism involves a key α -metallated carbonyl intermediate, decomposing to saturated keto-lactone, or rearranging into octahydrochromone by-product. The chromone backbone is presumably formed by intramolecular nucleophilic attack of the ester group by alkyl palladium moiety followed by reductive demetallation. Lactones with an allylic hydroxyl group at C-7 are involved in this catalytic cycle via metal catalyzed double bond migration followed by deprotonation and insertion of the resulting enol-palladium complex into the corresponding alpha-metallated ketone. The key intermediate in the form of palladium enolate is also highly plausible because such transition metal enolates are considered as reactive species in tandem reactions with electrophiles⁴⁸ such as an ester group in the current case (figure 14).

It is worth mentioning that dihydrostadenolide A (**26**) also contains an impurity with the NMR profile resembling the chromones presented here. Separation of this proposed chromone by-product was not achieved due to its decomposition during chromatographic purification on silica or using HPLC. In addition, this impurity apparently has the same molecular mass if it was formed via the same transannulation route described in figure 14. The evidence was initially overlooked during the TLC examination as differences of the R_f values for both of the isomerization products are hardly distinguishable.

Table 2. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data of compounds **32**, **34** and **36** in CDCl_3 (400 and 100 MHz, respectively)

position	Compound 32		Compound 34		Compound 36	
	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)
2	76.4, CH	3.87, m	68.7, CH	3.81, m	77.0, CH	3.89, dd (5.1, 1.8)
3	76.6, CH	3.87, m	71.5, CH	3.30, dd (9.8, 3.3)	76.4, CH	3.89, dd (5.1, 1.8)
4	207.4, C	-	72.5, CH	3.93, s	207.7, C	-
4a	50.5, CH	2.91, dd (12.1, 3.3)	40.0, CH	1.88, m	49.7, CH	3.02, dd (11.3, 3.3)
5	20.6, CH ₂	1.84, 1.74, m	25.2, CH ₂	1.55, 1.88, m	20.7, CH ₂	1.80, 1.65, m
6	18.7, CH ₂	1.67, 1.54, m	19.9, CH ₂	1.63, m	18.1, CH ₂	1.62, m
7	27.3, CH ₂	1.88, 1.79, m	27.7, CH ₂	1.76, 1.95, m	28.0, CH ₂	1.87, 1.77, m
8	72.3, CH	5.02, t (2.9)	71.9, CH	4.87, t (2.8)	72.7, CH	3.70, t (2.8)
8a	99.0, C	-	96.5, C	-	100.7, C	-
9	35.0, CH ₂	1.87, 1.65, m	33.9, CH ₂	1.48, 1.76, m	35.1, CH ₂	1.94, 1.72, m
10	18.2, CH ₂	1.53, 1.39, m	18.1, CH ₂	1.34, 1.48, m	18.5, CH ₂	1.61, 1.43, m
11	13.9, CH ₃	0.93, t (7.1)	13.9, CH ₃	0.92, t (7.2)	14.0, CH ₃	0.98, t (7.4)
1'	172.8, C	-	172.8, C	-	-	-
2'	34.6, CH ₂	2.38, t (7.4)	34.7, CH ₂	2.31, t (7.4)	-	-
3'	24.9, CH ₂	1.68, m	24.8, CH ₂	1.63, m	-	-
4'	31.2, CH ₂	1.37, m	31.2, CH ₂	1.34, m	-	-
5'	22.3, CH ₂	1.37, m	22.3, CH ₂	1.34, m	-	-
6'	14.0, CH ₃	0.94, t (7.4)	14.2, CH ₃	0.92, t (7.2)	-	-
OH (3)	-	3.55, s	-	2.40, bs	-	3.56, s
OH (4)	-	-	-	4.48, s	-	-
OH (8)	-	-	-	-	-	1.66, s
OH (8a)	-	2.45, s	-	3.49, bs	-	2.53, bs

Figure 14. Proposed mechanism for Pd-H catalyzed allylic transposition and transannulation of pinolidoxin **5**, 2-*epi*-herbarumin II (**6**) and their C-7 oxidized derivatives **8,10**

As shown for the compound **30**, metal-catalysed transposition does not proceed if the allylic OH group is acetylated. In the same manner, we synthesized acetylates of pinolidoxin to probe the link between Pd-catalyzed transposition and transannulation reactions.

Similarly to herbarumin I (**1**)¹¹, pinolidoxin **5** is acetylated with C-8 regioselectivity, thus two equivalents of acetic anhydride afforded monoacetate **37** as a major product with 53% yield and traces of diacetate. Meanwhile, preparation of diacetylpinolidoxin **38** in sufficient quantity requires a larger excess of acetic anhydride (figure 10). Compound **37** is considered a regioisomer of bellidisin B, the pinolidoxin C-7 monoacetate isolated from *Phoma bellidis* by Wang et al.⁴¹. However, bellidisin B was not formed as a semisynthetic by-product of acetylation under the discussed conditions. Previously, bis(acetyl)pinolidoxin **38** was prepared by Evidente et al.²⁴. The available data concerning the compound **38** have been supplemented with a complete NMR spectra description (presented in the supplementary file).

As expected, hydrogenation of the ester **38** affords only the saturated lactone **39** with the isolated yield of 97%. This evidence indicates that the allylic transposition and the C-1–C-6 transannulation are probably connected as none of these reactions took place for diacetyl bis(acetyl)pinolidoxin **38**.

In this section we demonstrated that hydrogen-activated metals like palladium or platinum induce isomerization of lactones **1-2**, **5-6**, **8** and **10** to keto-lactones and chromones. These stereospecific reactions compete with conventional hydrogenation. Chemoselectivity of the process depends on the

lactone structure as well as accessibility of the allylic hydroxyl group. We assume that such tandem addition-transannulation reactions may be a chemical trait of herbarumin I, stagonolide A, and related TMLs and therefore, should be considered in future studies.

Transannulation in protic media

As mentioned above, stagonolide A (**2**) reacts stereospecifically with sodium borohydride to form herbarumin I (**1**). For an attempt to synthesize its C-7 epimer **3**, a nonconventional reducing agent was used – namely, *Daucus carota* tissue. *D. carota* is known to reduce ketones into alcohols with high stereoselectivity⁴⁹⁻⁵¹, while enzymes isolated from it are capable of catalyzing an asymmetric cross aldol reaction and Henry reaction⁵²⁻⁵³. The grinded root was added to the solution of **2** in ethanol. However, instead of compound **3** or **1**, the reaction mixture consisted of stagonolide A (**2**) isomerization products. The major component was stagochromene A (**40**), a chromone-type compound that had previously been identified as a natural substance³³. This evidence demonstrates a direct relation between **2** and **40** and casts reasonable doubt on the biosynthetic origin of the latter (figure 14).

Figure 15. Isomerisation of stagonolide A (**2**) into stagochromene A (**40**) in the presence of *D. carota* roots

Comparative experiments showed that protic solvents significantly increased the reaction rate compared to aprotic ones. Triethylamine, on the contrary, led to decomposition of stagonolide A (**2**) without compound **40** being formed, while acetonitrile prevented lactone **2** from reacting altogether. Notably, lactone **2** decomposes slowly in alcohol and aqueous solutions in the absence of *D. carota* tissue additives. However, the process lacks sufficient chemoselectivity or yields lesser amounts of chromone **40**. The catalytic effect of *D. carota* ground roots was initially assumed to be associated with the enzyme components of the plant. Further variation of reaction conditions disproved this hypothesis. The dried carrot tissue had no impact on the reaction progress, whereas a purified ethanol extract of the freshly

ground roots had a catalytic effect similar to the raw plant material. This extract also gave a negative result for the ninhydrin test. Qualitative analysis using NMR spectroscopy revealed that the extract consists of a complex mixture of mono- and oligosaccharides as well as various polyols (see supplementary materials), most of which have been already described as the carbohydrate fraction components found in carrots⁵⁴. Another important feature of *D.carota* roots is high water content⁵⁵. Consequently, fresh root grinding releases this excessive water, diluting ethanol solution and facilitating extraction of polar compounds from the plant material. And since the carbohydrate fraction that is an extract was added to the reaction in aqueous solution, the effect of water on the reaction progress needs to be carefully distinguished as well.

The quantitative HPLC coupled with qualitative TLC investigation of the reaction mixture at various conditions was performed (figure 16). The aim was to find optimal media for the compound **40** preparation considering solvent sensitivity of the isomerisation. Thus the samples of lactone **2** were dissolved in 96% ethanol mixed with an aqueous solution of *D.carota* extract or mixed with finely chopped *D.carota* roots. Consequently, the ethanol concentration is diluted to 83% in these experiments involving carrot tissue or its extract. To eliminate the impact of water from our observations we conducted the control experiments with solutions of stagonolide A (**2**) in 83% and 4% aqueous ethanol without added carrots. The control solution of lactone **2** in acetonitrile was used to exclude spontaneous decomposition unrelated to protic solvents.

Figure 16. Quantitative HPLC evaluation of stagonolide A (**2**) isomerisation into stagochromene A (**40**) at various conditions: (A) consumption of lactone **2**; (B) formation of chromene **40**

As shown in the figure 16, stagonolide A (**2**) readily decomposes in the protic solvents. The process occurs three times faster in the presence of carrot root tissue and its carbohydrate fraction additives. Remarkably, *D.carota* as well as its extract provide the highest concentrations of stagochromene A (**40**) compared to the experiments without carrot. Whereas the excessive water content results in the parabolic concentration curve representing the substantial drop of the product quantity over time. Apparently further transformations take place yielding the isomers of the chromone **40**. The by-products were not separated and obtained in a sufficiently pure form and therefore, will not be discussed

here. However, their retention parameters and mass/UV-Vis spectra are shown in the supplemental materials.

Subsequently, the reactions were performed under *D.carota* extract exposure. It allowed us to obtain stagochromene A (**40**) with 36% isolated yield. This method was also applied to the related C-7 oxidized analogs **8,10-11,41**. Two derivatives were obtained as a result – 3-acetylstagochromene A (**42**) and compound **43** we called stagochromene K – with 28 and 36% yields respectively. The lactones with substituents at C-2 didn't form the corresponding chromones. Unlike stagochromene A (**40**), derivatives **42-43** do not form tautomeric mixtures in the *d3*-chloroform solution according to NMR data. An alternative synthetic route to 3-acetylstagochromene A (**42**) via acetylation of the chromone **40** allowed us to establish that the molecules **40** and **42** possess identical stereo configurations at C-3 and C-8a chiral centers. The diacetylated by-product **44** was also obtained with 51% yield as a result (figure 17).

Figure 17. Synthesis of chromones **40**, **42-44** from lactones **2**, **8**, **10-11**, **41** using *D.carota* extract as a catalyst. Reagents and conditions: (i) *D.carota* extract, 83% EtOH/H₂O (v/v), 72 h, rt; (ii) 20 equiv of Ac₂O, pyridine, rt

HRESIMS data confirmed their molecular formulas as follows: C₁₄H₂₀O₅ for compound **42** (291.1208 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd for C₁₄H₂₀O₅Na, 291.1203)), C₁₂H₁₈O₃ for compound **43** (231.0996 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd for C₁₂H₁₈O₃Na, 231.0992)) and C₁₆H₂₂O₆ for compound **44** (333.1313 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd for C₁₆H₂₂O₆Na, 333.1309)). Compounds **42-44** are structurally similar to the enol form of stagochromene A (**40**), thus having a rigid bicyclic backbone with the embedded β-diketone (figure 18, table 3). Their NMR spectra reveal two spin systems: the C-6–C-8a fragment (C-6 at δ 30.8, C-7 at δ 18.2, C-8 at δ 29.4, C-8a at δ 74.1 for compound **42**; C-6 at δ 31.8, C-7 at δ 18.1, C-8 at δ 29.6, C-8a at δ 74.08 for compound **43**;

C-6 at δ 29.0, C-7 at δ 18.3, C-8 at δ 28.6, C-8a at δ 75.1 for compound **44**) and the C-2–C-3 fragment attached to the C-9–C-11 propyl group (C-2 at δ 76.5, C-3 at δ 72.2, C-9 at δ 35.1, C-10 at δ 18.3, C-11 at δ 13.9 for compound **42**; C-2 at δ 74.11, C-3 at δ 39.7, C-9 at δ 38.4, C-10 at δ 18.5, C-11 at δ 14.0 for compound **43**; C-2 at δ 77.1, C-3 at δ 76.7, C-9 at δ 34.9, C-10 at δ 18.1, C-11 at δ 13.9 for compound **44**). The key HMBC correlations are observed between H-2/C-8a, H-3/C-4, H-3/C-1', H-6/C-5, H-6/C-4a, H-8a/C-2, H-8a/C-4a, H-8a/C-5, OH-5/C-3, OH-5/C-4, OH-5/C-4a, OH-5/C-5 and OH-5/C-6 for compound **42**; between H-3/C-4, H-3/C-4a, H-6/C-5, H-6/C-4a, H-8a/C-2, H-8a/C-4a, H-8a/C-5, OH-5/C-3, OH-5/C-4, OH-5/C-4a, OH-5/C-5 and OH-5/C-6 for compound **43**; between H-2/C-8a, H-3/C-4, H-3/C-1', H-6/C-5, H-6/C-4a, H-7/C-4a, H-8a/C-5 for compounds **44**. Hence these spin systems are connected by the β -diketone scaffold (C-4 at δ 188.0, C-4a at δ 110.2, C-5 δ 184.4 for compound **42**; C-4 at δ 189.8, C-4a at δ 110.1, C-5 δ 187.1 for compound **43**; C-4 at δ 190.2, C-4a at δ 123.4, C-5 δ 155.1 for compound **44**) within the chromone core. These correlations allowed us to identify the acetyl residue attached to the C-3 atom (C-1' at δ 172.8, C-2'' at δ 20.7 for the acetate **42**; C-1' at δ 169.7, C-2'' at δ 20.8 for the acetate **44**). Similar to stagochromene A (**40**), the protons H-2 and H-8a of chromones **42-44** have an axial arrangement, as shown by the axial-axial coupling constant in the ^1H NMR spectra ($^3J_{\text{H-H}}$ 10 Hz). Axial arrangement of the proton H-2 in stagochromene K (**43**) was indirectly deduced from the signal of the proton H-3 at δ 2.34 also showing J value of 10 Hz. For all three chromones **42-44**, the NOESY correlations are observed between H-2/H-8a. Chromone **42** also has H-2/H-9 and H-6/H-8a correlations, whereas only H-2/H-9 correlation was observed for compound **44**. This evidence supports *cis*-arrangement of H-2 and H-8a protons. Thus, taking into account differences in C-9 configuration of the initial lactones and previous data on stagochromene A (**40**)³³, we proposed the following relative configuration of chiral atoms in newly synthesised chromones: $2R^*$, $3R^*$, $8aS^*$ for the acetates **42** and **44**, $2S^*$, $8aR^*$ for stagochromene K (**43**).

Figure 18. Key 2D NMR correlations of compounds **42-44**

Table 3. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data of compounds **42-44** in CDCl_3 (400 and 100 MHz, respectively)

position	Compound 42		Compound 43		Compound 44	
	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)
2	76.5, CH	3.78, ddd (9.7, 8.2, 3.0)	74.11, CH	3.75, m	77.1, CH	3.75, ddd (10.2, 8.0, 1.6)
3	72.2, CH	5.06, d (9.7)	39.7, CH ₂	2.44, m 2.34, dd (18.5, 10.4)	76.7, CH	4.96, d (10.2)
4	188.0, C	-	189.8, C	-	190.2, C	-
4a	110.2, C	-	110.1, C	-	123.4, C	-
5	184.4, C	-	187.1, C	-	155.1, C	-
6	30.8, CH ₂	2.44, m	31.8, CH ₂	2.43, m	29.0, CH ₂	2.31, m
7	18.2, CH ₂	1.97, 1.66 m	18.1, CH ₂	1.95, m	18.3, CH ₂	1.90, 1.71, m
8	29.4, CH ₂	2.15, 1.52, m	29.6, CH ₂	2.17, 1.50, m	28.6, CH ₂	2.17, 1.61, m
8a	74.1, CH	4.39, dd (10.8, 4.8)	74.08, CH	4.30, dd (10.9, 4.8)	75.1, CH	4.40, m
9	35.1, CH ₂	1.56, m	38.4, CH ₂	1.66, 1.46, m	34.9, CH ₂	1.56, m
10	18.3, CH ₂	1.59, 1.41, m	18.5, CH ₂	1.44, m	18.1, CH ₂	1.58, 1.41, m
11	13.9, CH ₃	0.96, t (7.1)	14.0, CH ₃	0.96, t (7.1)	13.9, CH ₃	0.94, t (7.0)
1'	170.0, C	-	-	-	169.7, C	-
2'	20.7, CH ₃	2.18, s	-	-	20.8, CH ₃	2.18, bs
1''	-	-	-	-	168.5, C	-
2''	-	-	-	-	20.6, CH ₃	2.18, bs

The absolute configuration of the chromones **40**, **42** and **44** was determined by CD-spectroscopy. 3-Acetylstagochromene A (**42**) was used as a reference compound since all three chromones are of the same chemical origin and hence, share the identical set of stereo descriptors. The experimental ECD spectrum of compound **42** (black line) displays a broad positive Cotton effect centered at approximately 290 nm, along with a second positive band around 240 nm, showing a subtle inflection near 250 nm. These are accompanied by a weaker negative feature near 210 nm, and a discernible but low-intensity positive band at 200 nm. Among the three calculated spectra, the one corresponding to the 2*R*,3*R*,8*aS* stereoisomer (red dashed line) shows the best agreement with the experimental data, accurately reproducing both the sign and shape of the key Cotton effects. In contrast, the alternative stereoisomers display marked deviations, particularly in the 240–300 nm region, failing to match the experimental spectral profile (figure 19). These results strongly support the 2*R*, 3*R*, 8*aS* absolute configuration for 3-acetylstagochromene A (**42**) as well as for its structurally related stagochromene A (**40**) and bis(acetyl)stagochromene A (**44**).

Figure 19. Theoretical and experimental ECD spectra of compound **42**

The CD spectrum of stagochromene K (**43**) yielded ambiguous results. However, a comparison with stagonolide A (**2**) and its analogue, C-7 oxidized stagonolide K (**11**), reveals key stereochemical differences: in C-7 oxidized stagonolide K, the stereocenter at C-9 is inverted, and the plane of the C=C bond is flipped by 180°, resulting in protons H-5, H-6, and H-9 pointing in opposite directions between the two molecules. Based on the mechanistic rationale discussed below (figure 20), we infer that stagochromenes A (**40**) and K (**43**) bear opposite set of stereodescriptors at the newly formed chiral centers C-2 and C-8a, which derive respectively from the C-5 and C-9 positions of the parent lactones. Accordingly, the absolute configuration of stagochromene K (**43**) is assigned as 2S, 8aR.

Our calculations on stagonolide A (**2**) isomerization suggest that first, a water molecule participates in a 1,4-addition to the C=C double bond via the 6-membered transition state (TS-2-A) forming an enol (intermediate A), after which the enol does a transannular nucleophilic attack on the ester carbonyl while the O atom from the ester group attacks the COH fragment of the enol via a 4-membered cyclic transition state (TS-A-B), forming a ketone and a dihydroxy-oxetane (intermediate B). Then, the hemiacetal OH group's proton is transferred to the oxetane O atom via yet another 4-membered transition state (TS-B-C), leading to the ring opening and the formation of a ketone and an OH group (intermediate C). In the last isomerization step, this intermediate undergoes a rather unorthodox spontaneous dehydration-cyclization via transition state TS-C-40 (figure 20). The lability of the hydroxyl in this case is presumably caused by the formation of the stable carbocation, capable of charge delocalisation with the participation of a diketone.

The role of *D.carota* extract in this process, however, is not clear. Nevertheless one study reports on catalytic properties of aldoses in mild and chemoselective hydration of α -aminonitriles⁵⁶.

Figure 20. Mechanistic pathway and calculated energy profile (ΔG , kcal/mol) for the conversion of stagonolide A (**2**) to stagochromene A (**40**), highlighting key transition states and intermediates involved in the transannular rearrangement cascade

The *oxa*-Michael addition of water to presaccharothriolide X, previously reported by Lu and co-workers³¹, resembles the first stage of the transannulation process proposed for compound **2**. Further transformations of the resulting saccharothriolide C are presumably hindered by the insufficient spatial proximity between the ester group and the C-6 atom, as well as by steric shielding from the adjacent methyl substituent.

Transannulation of stagonolide A (**2**) and its structural analogs into the corresponding hexahydro-4H-chromen-4-ones provides a rare example of the middle sized cyclic polyketides isomerisation. Such transformations raise concerns about stability of these TMLs during long-term storage – especially in protic solvents – and may potentially be a part of the degradation pathways of these phytotoxins in the environment. The tendency of C-5–C-6 unsaturated TMLs to form fused six-membered heterocycles could potentially be persistent and take place in other reactions involving this electron deficient carbon-carbon double bond.

Dimerization

Previous studies have demonstrated a correlation between the presence of the α,β -unsaturated keto group in TML molecules and their broad-spectrum toxicity¹¹⁻¹². To disrupt the conjugation between the carbonyl group and the adjacent C=C double bond in stagonolide A (**2**), pinolidoxone **8**, and 2-hydroxystagonolide A (**10**), the Lobry de Bruyn-Van Ekenstein reaction was employed⁵⁷. Sodium *tert*-butylate was used as the base and tetrahydrofuran (THF) served as the solvent. However, instead of isomerization, a novel reaction pathway was observed. Lactones **2**, **8**, and **10** yielded the corresponding dimerization products **45-47** with isolated yields ranging from 35 to 81%. These products share a tetrahydrofuran moiety, which presumably formed via intermolecular condensation between two identical lactone units (figure 21).

Figure 21. Base catalyzed Morita–Baylis–Hillman-like dimerisation of compounds **2**, **8**, **10**

Despite the formation of three new stereogenic centers, the reaction proceeds stereospecifically as no diastereomeric by-products were detected or isolated from the reaction mixture. However, the synthesis requires low temperatures to avoid base-catalysed decomposition of the reaction components. As described in previous subsections, the perpendicularity between the olefinic plane and the plane of the lactone ring predisposes peripheral attack on the C-5–C-6 double bond. This effect also extends to the initial lactones **2**, **8**, **10**, which contain a rigid region of the conjugated carbonyl group. Such conformational features, along with highly limited torsional rotation within cycles are presumably

responsible for the observed stereospecificity. It allowed reliable prediction of the *trans*-orientation of protons at the C-2 and C-11 chiral centers in the resulting dimers **45-47**. The hypothesis was further supported by analysis of NOE correlation patterns in their NMR spectra.

HRESIMS data confirmed their molecular formulae as follows: $C_{24}H_{36}O_8$ for compound **45** (475.2305 $[M + Na]^+$ (calcd for $C_{24}H_{36}O_8Na$, 475.2302)), $C_{36}H_{48}O_{12}$ for compound **46** (695.3030 $[M + Na]^+$ (calcd for $C_{36}H_{48}O_{12}Na$, 695.3038)) and $C_{24}H_{36}O_{10}$ for compound **47** (507.2209 $[M + Na]^+$ (calcd for $C_{24}H_{36}O_{10}Na$, 507.2201)). 2D NMR analysis of compounds **45-47** reveals tricyclic fused structures with highly substituted tetrahydrofurane in the middle (figure 22, table 4). The cycle A comprises two spin systems: C-17–C-21 fragment (C-17 at δ 34.1, C-18 at δ 25.5, C-19 at δ 33.4, C-20 at δ 131.9, C-21 at δ 129.7 for compound **45**; C-17 at δ 69.6, C-18 at δ 30.7, C-19 at δ 27.6, C-20 at δ 130.7, C-21 at δ 130.9 for compound **46**; C-17 at δ 69.7, C-18 at δ 32.2, C-19 at δ 26.5, C-20 at δ 131.5, C-21 at δ 130.4 for compound **47**) and C-13–C-14 fragment with a propyl group attached (C-13 at δ 84.37, C-14 at δ 70.1, C-25 at δ 33.7, C-26 at δ 19.3, C-27 at δ 13.73 for compound **45**; C-13 at δ 85.2, C-14 at δ 71.2, C-25 at δ 33.6, C-26 at δ 17.5, C-27 at δ 13.7 for compound **46**; C-13 at δ 84.6, C-14 at δ 71.4, C-25 at δ 33.7, C-26 at δ 17.8, C-27 at δ 13.7 for compound **47**). The cycle C also hosts two spin systems: C-2, C-8–C-11 fragment (C-2 at δ 66.9, C-8 at δ 34.9, C-9 at δ 19.3, C-10 at δ 35.1, C-11 at δ 76.6 for compound **45**; C-2 at δ 64.3, C-8 at δ 71.8, C-9 at δ 26.2, C-10 at δ 27.9, C-11 at δ 78.4 for compound **46**; C-2 at δ 64.6, C-8 at δ 70.3, C-9 at δ 28.8, C-10 at δ 27.5, C-11 at δ 78.3 for compound **47**) and C-3–C-4 fragment with a propyl group attached (C-3 at δ 207.2, C-4 at δ 80.6, C-22 at δ 33.9, C-23 at δ 18.3, C-24 at δ 13.7 for compound **45**; C-3 at δ 207.3, C-4 at δ 78.6, C-22 at δ 34.0, C-23 at δ 18.0, C-24 at δ 13.6 for compound **46**; C-3 at δ 207.8, C-4 at δ 77.9, C-22 at δ 33.9, C-23 at δ 18.3, C-24 at δ 13.6 for compound **47**). These four spin systems are linked together via the ester group (C-16 at δ 177.2 for dimer **45**, at δ 171.9 for dimer **46**, at δ 173.8 for dimer **47**), the tertiary alcohol carbon (C-1 at δ 84.43 for dimer **45**, at δ 83.0 for dimers **46-47**) within the cycle A, the carbonyl carbon (C-3 at δ 207.2 for dimer **45**, at δ 207.3 for dimer **46**, at δ 207.8 for dimer **47**) and the ester group (C-7 at δ 171.5 for dimer **45**, at δ 169.1 for dimer **46**, at δ 172.3 for dimer **47**) within the cycle C, and the ether oxygen atom O-12. The key HMBC correlations are observed for OH-1/C-21, H-2/C-1, H-2/C-3, H-2/C-4, H-2/C-21, H-4/C-3, H-5/C-7, H-8/C-7, H-9/C-7, H-11/C-3, H-11/C-13, H-13/C-1, H-13/C-21, H-14/C-16, H-17/C-16, H-18/C-16, H-20/C-1, H-21/C-1 for dimer **45**; for H-2/C-1, H-2/C-3, H-2/C-21, H-4/C-3, H-5/C-7, H-8/C-7, H-13/C-1, H-14/C-16, H-17/C-16, H-17/C-1'', H-20/C-1, H-21/C-1, H-2''/C-1', H-3'/C-1', H-2''/C-1'', H-3''/C-1'' for dimer **46**; for H-2/C-1, H-2/C-3, H-2/C-21, H-4/C-3, H-5/C-7, H-8/C-7, H-9/C-7, H-13/C-1, H-13/C-21, H-14/C-1, H-14/C-16, H-17/C-16, H-20/C-1, H-21/C-1, H-21/C-13 for dimer **47**. The key NOESY correlations are observed for H-2/H-4, H-2/H-13, H-2/H-21, H-4/H-23, H-4/H-21, H-13/H-21 for dimer **45**; for H-2/H-4, H-2/H-13, H-2/H-21, H-11/OH-1, H-13/H-21, H-14/OH-1, H-18/H-20, H-20/OH-1, for dimer **46**; for H-2/H-4, H-2/H-21, H-13/H-10, H-13/H-21, H-13/H-26, OH-1/H-14 for dimer **47**. This repetitive correlation patterns and the previously studied stereo arrangement of substituents in the initial lactones

enabled the assignment of 1R*,2R*,11R* relative configurations for newly formed chiral centres in compounds **45-47** (figure 22, table 4).

Figure 22. Key 2D NMR correlations of compounds **45-47**

Table 4. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR data of compounds **45-47** in CDCl_3 (400 and 100 MHz, respectively)

position	Compound 45		Compound 46		Compound 47	
	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)	δ_{C} , type	δ_{H} (J in Hz)
1	84.43, C	-	83.0, C	-	83.0, C	-
2	66.9, CH	3.11, d (6.9)	64.3, CH	3.36, d (8.3)	64.6, CH	3.51, d (7.2)
3	207.2, C	-	207.3, C	-	207.8, C	-
4	80.6,	4.12, t (2.8)	78.6, CH	4.14, d (6.4)	77.9, CH	4.12, d (7.1)

	CH					
5	77.3, CH	5.19, m	78.6, CH	4.82, m	78.6, CH	4.78, td (7.9, 4.4)
7	171.5, C	-	169.1, C	-	172.3, C	-
8	34.9, CH2	2.55, 2.34, m	71.8, CH	5.06, dd (7.8, 3.1)	70.3, CH	4.37, dd* (8.6, 2.8)
9	19.3, CH2	1.77, m	26.2, CH2	2.09, m	28.8, CH2	2.06, m
10	35.1, CH2	1.76, m	27.9, CH2	2.11, 1.75, m	27.5, CH2	2.16, 1.66, m
11	76.6, CH	5.26, m	78.4, CH	4.83, m	78.3, CH	4.68, m
13	84.37, CH	3.50, d (9.3)	85.2, CH	3.57, d (9.5)	84.6, CH	3.66, d (9.4)
14	70.1, CH	5.08, td (9.4, 2.5)	71.2, CH	5.19, td (9.2, 2.3)	71.4, CH	5.28, td (9.4, 2.6)
16	177.2, C	-	171.9, C	-	173.8, C	-
17	34.1, CH2	2.38, 1.99, m	69.6, CH	5.32, d (4.0)	69.7, CH	4.38, dd* (5.1, 1.8)
18	25.5, CH2	1.99, 1.82, m	30.7, CH2	2.29, 2.07, m	32.2, CH2	2.11, m
19	33.4, CH2	2.46, 1.98, m	27.6, CH2	2.43, 2.31, m	26.5, CH2	2.50, ddd (24.1, 12.6, 4.3), 2.20, m
20	131.9, CH	5.60, ddd (15.5, 10.2, 3.7)	130.7, CH	5.70, m	131.5, CH	5.72, ddd (15.5, 10.9, 3.2)
21	129.7, CH	5.50, d (15.7)	130.9, CH	5.59, d (15.5)	130.4, CH	5.64, d (15.5)
22	33.9, CH2	1.72, m	34.0, CH2	1.81, m	33.9, CH2	1.91, m
23	18.3, CH2	1.34, m	18.0, CH2	1.32, m	18.3, CH2	1.42, m
24	13.7, CH3	0.94, t (7.4)	13.6, CH3	0.91, t (6.9)	13.6, CH3	0.96, t (7.7)
25	33.7, CH2	1.79, 1.60, m	33.6, CH2	1.69, 1.51, m	33.7, CH2	1.79, 1.62, m
26	17.9, CH2	1.36, m	17.5, CH2	1.31, m	17.8, CH2	1.37, m
27	13.73, CH3	0.95, t (7.4)	13.7, CH3	0.89, t (7.0)	13.7, CH3	0.94, t (7.7)
1'	-	-	166.1, C	-	-	-
2'	-	-	117.3, CH	5.86, d (15.3)	-	-
3'	-	-	146.7, CH	7.33, m	-	-
4'	-	-	129.7, CH	6.26, m	-	-
5'	-	-	140.8, CH	6.26, m	-	-
6'	-	-	18.7, CH3	1.91, d (4.8)	-	-
1''	-	-	166.0, C	-	-	-
2''	-	-	118.0, CH	5.91, d (15.5)	-	-

3''	-	-	146.1, CH	7.36, m	-	-
4''	-	-	129.6, CH	6.26, m	-	-
5''	-	-	140.4, CH	6.26, m	-	-
6''	-	-	18.7, CH ₃	1.93, d (5.0)	-	-
OH (1)	-	3.37, s	-	2.96, s	-	2.82, s
OH (4)	-	4.51, bs	-	3.71, bs	-	3.55, s

*signals partially obscured

Absolute configuration assignment and mechanistic studies were conducted using the dimer **45** as a reference compound. Its experimental ECD spectrum exhibits a strong positive Cotton effect at 187 nm, a smaller positive feature near 248 nm, and a broad negative band around 299 nm, with a slight inflection near 220 nm corresponding to the crossover between adjacent bands. Comparison with calculated spectra confirms the 1R,2R,4R,5R,11R,13R,14R configuration, consistent with contributions from multiple spatially proximate but electronically independent chromophores (figure 23A). Consequently, both dimers **46-47** possess the 1R,2R,4R,5R,8S,11R,13R,14R,17S absolute configuration because they have originated as a result of the same reaction as the compound **45**.

Figure 23. (A) Theoretical and experimental ECD spectra of compound **45**. (B) Proposed TS for stagonolide A (**2**) dimerization reaction

The proposed mechanism resembles that of the Morita-Baylis-Hillman reaction⁵⁸. However, instead of a tertiary amine or phosphine, it is the deprotonated OH group at C-8 that acts as a nucleophile to attack the β -position of another molecule. This is followed by intramolecular enolate trapping by the carbonyl group to form the final adduct. Unlike the conventional Morita-Baylis-Hillman reaction, this process does not regenerate the initial enone upon elimination of the nucleophile, so the furan moiety is retained (figure 24).

Figure 24. Proposed mechanism of stagonolide A (**2**) dimerization

In contrast to the Lobry de Bruyn-Van Ekenstein reaction, in this case, proton transfer from 8-OH to the carbonyl group is accompanied by annulation with the neighbouring lactone molecule. Specific arrangement of functional groups at the C-5–C-8 region of lactones **2**, **8**, **10** makes them particularly susceptible to this process. The *tert*-butoxide ion has been shown to significantly facilitate this transfer, as no barrier was detected in its presence during transition state calculations. The pericyclic transition state was obtained only in a protonated system. This state comprises two stagonolide A (**2**) cycles that are aligned in such a manner that the O-8 and C-7 atoms of one molecule are in close proximity to the C-5 and C-6 atoms of another. The proton involved in this transition appears to be delocalized equally between the oxygen atoms at the C-7 and C-8 positions (figure 23B). The base can either facilitate the delocalization of the proton or directly transfer it, thus supporting the proposed reaction mechanism (figure 24).

Although Morita-Baylis-Hillman-like reactions are occasionally known to form annulation⁵⁹⁻⁶⁰ and dimerization⁶¹⁻⁶² products, the example presented here is proposed as a new unconventional type. This reaction also adds to the limited set of known non-enzymatic dimerizations of fungal polyketides such as (+)-(10E,15R)-10,11-dehydrocurvularin⁶³, indigotide A and chaetophenol B⁶⁴, chaetophenol I⁶⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

General experimental procedures, including fungal strain and toxin production, quantitative HPLC analysis of natural lactones and their semisynthetic derivatives, preparation methods of semisynthetic derivatives and their spectroscopic data, X-ray data as well computational details are available in the Supporting Information.

CONCLUSION

Fungal ten-membered lactones (TMLs) are promising candidates for agrochemical discovery due to their structural simplicity and a broad range of biological effects relevant for crop protection. Despite extensive research on their isolation, total synthesis, biological profiling, and structure-activity relationship, scarce data on their chemistry is available. To address this gap, we explored chemical properties of herbarumin I, 2-*epi*-herbarumin II, stagonolides J-K, pinolidoxin, and their C-7 oxidized analogs under oxidation, hydrogenation, and isomerisation reactions. As a result, structure-reactivity patterns have been formulated. We found that TMLs with glycol moiety undergo C-7–C-8 oxidative cleavage under manganese-based oxidants. Conformational analysis of TMLs possessing an allylic alcohol group yielded a plausible explanation of their ability to undergo stereospecific Prilezhaev epoxidation at the C-5–C-6 position. Metals such as palladium or platinum activated by hydrogen catalyze allylic transposition and transannulation of TMLs, forming unusual chromone-like by-products. Stagonolide A and structurally-related lactones containing α,β -unsaturated ketone isomerize into chromones via transannulation in protic media in the presence of *D.carota* extract. The interaction of a chemically distant but spatially close ester group with an olefin fragment predisposes the studied TMLs to intramolecular reactions. Additionally, Morita-Baylis-Hillman-like dimerisation of TMLs into fused tetrahydrofuran derivatives was discovered. Considering all of the above, we regard TMLs bearing electron-deficient C-5–C-6 double bond as reactive scaffolds, especially compounds like stagonolide A capable of undergoing both intra- and intermolecular reactions. This unique chemistry could be potentially exploited for synthesis of fused heterocycles and simultaneously raises a question of chemical stability of TMLs, informing future research.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI:.... General experimental procedures, including fungal strain and toxin production, quantitative HPLC analysis procedures for natural lactones and their semisynthetic derivatives, preparation methods of semisynthetic derivatives; HRESI MS spectra of compounds **7–10**, **15–23a,b**, **25–37**, **39–40**, **42–47**; NMR spectra of compounds **2**, **6–10**, **15–23a,b**, **25–40**, **42–47**; Crystallographic data of compounds **12–13**, **15** and **21**; ECD spectra of compounds **42** and **45**; NMR spectra of *D. carota* extract; UPLC chromatogram of compound **7**; Chromatographic and TLC data of compound **2** transannulation reaction progress under different conditions (PDF). Raw NMR data of compounds **7–10**, **15–23a,b**, **25–40**, **42–47** (zip). ORCA output files used for ECD calculations of compounds **42** and **45**; Preoptimized xyz geometries and ORCA output files of reactants, intermediates, transition states, and products for compound **2** transannulation and dimerisation reactions (zip). Raw crystallographic data of compounds **12–13**, **15** and **21** (zip).

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*(A.F.) E-mail: fedorganat@gmail.com

Funding

This research was funded by the Russian Science Foundation No. 22-16-00038. The support covered data acquisition performed by A. Fedorov, A. Dalinova, A. Alekseeva, A. Berestetskiy. All other authors declare that they did not receive any financial support from this source.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge Saint-Petersburg State University for a research project 125021702335-5, for NMR study. X-ray study was performed at the N. D. Zelinsky Institute of Organic Chemistry of Russian Academy of Sciences (Moscow, Russian Federation). HRMS studies were performed at the Center for Chemical Analysis and Materials Research of Saint Petersburg State University, Saint Petersburg, Russia.

References

- (1) Tyutereva, E. V.; Dalinova, A. A.; Demchenko, K. N.; Dmitrieva, V. A.; Dubovik, V. R.; Lukinskiy, Y. V.; Mitina, G. V.; Voitsekhovskaja, O. V.; Berestetskiy, A. Effects of Phytotoxic Nonenolides, Stagonolide A and Herbarumin I, on Physiological and Biochemical Processes in Leaves and Roots of Sensitive Plants. *Toxins* **2023**, *15* (4), 234–234. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins15040234>.
- (2) Han, W.; Zhai, Y.; Zhang, R.; Gong, X.; Li, J.; Xu, G.; Lei, X.; Du, L.; Gao, J. Tricrilactones A–H, Potent Antiosteoporosis Macrolides with Distinctive Ring Skeletons from *Trichocladium Crispatum*, an Alpine Moss-Associated Fungus. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **2023**, *62* (15). <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202300773>.
- (3) Li, X.; Chen, H.-P.; Zhou, L.; Fan, J.; Awakawa, T.; Mori, T.; Ushimaru, R.; Abe, I.; Liu, J.-K. Cordycicadins A–D, Antifeedant Polyketides from the Entomopathogenic Fungus *Cordyceps Cicadae* JXCH1. *Organic Letters* **2022**, *24* (47), 8627–8632. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.orglett.2c03432>.
- (4) Dubovik, V.; Dalinova, A.; Berestetskiy, A. Natural Ten-Membered Lactones: Sources, Structural Diversity, Biological Activity, and Intriguing Future. *Natural Product Reports* **2023**, *41* (1), 85–112. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3np00013c>.
- (5) Schmidt, B. The Role of Total Synthesis in Structure Revision and Elucidation of Decanolides (Nonanolides). *Fortschritte der Chemie Organischer Naturstoffe/Fortschritte der Chemie organischer Naturstoffe/Progress in the chemistry of organic natural products* **2021**, 1–57. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64853-4_1.

- (6) Ryo Katsuta. Advancement in Structure Elucidation of Natural Medium-Sized Lactones through Synthesis and Theoretical Calculations. *Bioscience Biotechnology and Biochemistry* **2023**, 88 (3), 260–269. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bbb/zbad179>.
- (7) Bassetti, M.; D'Annibale, A. Metathetic Synthesis of Common and Medium-Sized Lactones: The State of the Art. *Topics in heterocyclic chemistry* **2015**, 57–110. https://doi.org/10.1007/7081_2015_143.
- (8) Lebœuf, D.; Van Hoof, M.; Force, G. Modern Macrolactonization Techniques. *Synthesis* **2023**, 56 (05), 714–732. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-2181-9800>.
- (9) Wang, B.-C.; Wei, Y.; Xiong, F.-Y.; Qu, B.-L.; Xiao, W.-J.; Lu, L.-Q. Construction of Enantioenriched Eight-Membered Lactones via Pd-Catalyzed Asymmetric (6+2) Dipolar Annulation. *Science China Chemistry* **2022**, 65 (12), 2437–2443. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11426-022-1374-4>.
- (10) Berestetskiy, A. O.; Dalinova, A. A.; Dubovik, V. R. Strain *Stagonospora Cirsii* G-51 VIZR - producer of herbarumine I and stagonolide A. RU2701817C1, 2019.
- (11) Dalinova, A.; Fedorov, A.; Dubovik, V.; Voitsekhovskaja, O.; Tyutereva, E.; Smirnov, S.; Dmitry Kochura; Leonid Chisty; Igor Senderskiy; Berestetskiy, A. Structure–Activity Relationship of Phytotoxic Natural 10-Membered Lactones and Their Semisynthetic Derivatives. *Journal of Fungi* **2021**, 7 (10), 829–829. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof7100829>.
- (12) Fedorov, A.; Dubovik, V.; Smirnov, S.; Leonid Chisty; Khrustalev, V.; Slukin, A.; Alekseeva, A.; Stepanycheva, E.; Igor Senderskiy; Berestetskiy, A.; Dalinova, A. Structure–Activity Relationships of Natural C-9-Methyl-Substituted 10-Membered Lactones and Their Semisynthetic Derivatives. *Journal of Natural Products* **2024**, 87 (4), 914–923. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jnatprod.3c01216>.
- (13) Guan, A.; Liu, C.; Yang, X.; Dekeyser, M. Application of the Intermediate Derivatization Approach in Agrochemical Discovery. *Chemical Reviews* **2014**, 114 (14), 7079–7107. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr4005605>.
- (14) Riemenschneider, W.; Bolt, H. M. Esters, Organic. *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry* **2005**. https://doi.org/10.1002/14356007.a09_565.pub2.
- (15) Kobayashi, S. Enzymatic Ring-Opening Polymerization and Polycondensation for the Green Synthesis of Polyesters. *Polymers for Advanced Technologies* **2015**, 26 (7), 677–686. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pat.3564>.
- (16) Zhang, X.-Y.; Lu, K.; Guo, B.-K.; Shao, Y.-P.; Wang, H.; Zhang, F.-M.; Tu, Y.-Q.; Zhang, X.-M. Catalytic Enantioselective Steglich-Type Rearrangement of Enol Lactones: Asymmetric Synthesis of Spirocyclic 1,3-Diketones. *The Journal of Organic Chemistry* **2022**, 87 (22), 15031–15041. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.joc.2c01421>.

- (17) Oleksandr Zhurakovskiy; Ellis, S. R.; Thompson, A. L.; Robertson, J. Access to a Guanacastepene and Cortistatin-Related Skeleton via Ethynyl Lactone Ireland–Claisen Rearrangement and Transannular (4 + 3)-Cycloaddition of an Azatrimethylenemethane Diyl. *Organic Letters* **2017**, *19* (8), 2174–2177. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.orglett.7b00834>.
- (18) Funk, R. L.; Abelman, M. M.; Munger, J. D. Claisen-Rearrangement-Mediated Ring Contraction of Macrocyclic Lactones. *Tetrahedron* **1986**, *42* (11), 2831–2846. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0040-4020\(01\)90572-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0040-4020(01)90572-1).
- (19) Abelman, M. M.; Funk, R. L.; Munger, J. D. Alicyclic Claisen Rearrangement. A General Carbocycle Synthesis Based on Four-Atom-Ring Contractions of Lactones. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **1982**, *104* (14), 4030–4032. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00378a054>.
- (20) Alois Fürstner; Radkowski, K.; Wirtz, C.; Goddard, R.; Lehmann, C. W.; Mynott, R. Total Syntheses of the Phytotoxic Lactones Herbarumin I and II and a Synthesis-Based Solution of the Pinolidoxin Puzzle. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2002**, *124* (24), 7061–7069. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja020238i>.
- (21) Fausto Rivero-Cruz, J.; García-Aguirre G.; Cerda-García-Rojas C. M.; Mata, R. Conformational Behavior and Absolute Stereostructure of Two Phytotoxic Nonenolides from the Fungus *Phoma Herbarum*. *Tetrahedron* **2000**, *56* (30), 5337–5344. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0040-4020\(00\)00469-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0040-4020(00)00469-5).
- (22) Srihari, P.; Kumaraswamy, B.; Rao, G. M.; Yadav, J. S. First Stereoselective Total Synthesis of (–)-Stagonolide A. *Tetrahedron: Asymmetry* **2010**, *21* (1), 106–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tetasy.2009.12.015>.
- (23) Prabhakar, P.; Rajaram, S.; Reddy, D. K.; Shekar, V.; Venkateswarlu, Y. Total Synthesis of the Phytotoxic Stagonolides A and B. *Tetrahedron: Asymmetry* **2010**, *21* (2), 216–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tetasy.2010.01.010>.
- (24) Evidente, A.; Lanzetta, R.; Capasso, R.; Vurro, M.; Botralico, A. Pinolidoxin, a Phytotoxic Nonenolide from *Ascochyta Pinodes*. *Phytochemistry* **1993**, *34* (4), 999–1003. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0031-9422\(00\)90702-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0031-9422(00)90702-7).
- (25) Evidente, A. Putaminoxin, a Phytotoxic Nonenolide from *Phoma Putaminum*. *Phytochemistry* **1995**, *40* (6), 1637–1641. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-9422\(95\)00505-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-9422(95)00505-2).
- (26) Schmidt, B.; Kunz, O. Bidirectional Cross Metathesis and Ring-Closing Metathesis/Ring Opening of a C₂-Symmetric Building Block: A Strategy for the Synthesis of Decanolide Natural Products. *Beilstein Journal of Organic Chemistry* **2013**, *9*, 2544–2555. <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjoc.9.289>.
- (27) Masi, M.; Castaldi, S.; Sautua, F.; Gennaro Pescitelli; Carmona, M. A.; Evidente, A. Truncatenolide, a Bioactive Disubstituted Nonenolide Produced by *Colletotrichum Truncatum*, the Causal Agent of

Anthraco-nose of Soybean in Argentina: Fungal Antagonism and SAR Studies. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* **2022**, *70* (32), 9834–9844. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.2c02502>.

(28) Lu, S.; Sun, P.; Li, T.; Tibor Kurtán; Attila Mándi; Antus, S.; Krohn, K.; Draeger, S.; Schulz, B.; Yi, Y.-H.; Li, L.; Zhang, W. Bioactive Nonanolide Derivatives Isolated from the Endophytic Fungus *Cytospora* Sp.. *The Journal of Organic Chemistry* **2011**, *76* (23), 9699–9710. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jo201755v>.

(29) Lu, S.; Kurtán, T.; Yang, G.; Sun, P.; Mándi, A.; Krohn, K.; Draeger, S.; Schulz, B.; Yi, Y.; Li, L.; Zhang, W. Cytosporolides A–E, New Nonanolides from an Endophytic Fungus, *Cytospora* Sp.. *European Journal of Organic Chemistry* **2011**, *2011* (28), 5452–5459. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejoc.201100675>.

(30) Mayer, M.; Thiericke, R. A Non-Enzymatic Reaction in the Late Biosynthesis of the Decarestrictine Family. *The Journal of Antibiotics* **1993**, *46* (9), 1372–1380. <https://doi.org/10.7164/antibiotics.46.1372>.

(31) Lu, S.; Nishimura, S.; Takenaka, K.; Ito, M.; Kato, T.; Hideaki Kakeya. Discovery of Presaccharothriolide X, a Retro-Michael Reaction Product of Saccharothriolide B, from the Rare Actinomycete *Saccharothrix* Sp. A1506. *Organic Letters* **2018**, *20* (15), 4406–4410. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.orglett.8b01535>.

(32) Lu, S.; Ren, L.; Mao, D.; Hideaki Kakeya. Mechanistic Study of the Retro-Aza-Michael Reaction in Saccharothriolide L: Identification of 2-Amino-4-Methylphenol as an Effective Protecting Tool for the Michael Acceptor. *The Journal of Antibiotics* **2024**, *77* (8). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41429-024-00741-3>.

(33) Dalinova, A.; Dubovik, V.; Chisty, L.; Kochura, D.; Ivanov, A.; Smirnov, S.; Petrova, M.; Zolotarev, A.; Evidente, A.; Berestetskiy, A. Stagonolides J and K and Stagochromene A, Two New Natural Substituted Nonenolides and a New Disubstituted Chromene-4,5-Dione Isolated from *Stagonospora Cirsii* S-47 Proposed for the Biocontrol of *Sonchus Arvensis*. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry* **2019**, *67* (47), 13040–13050. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.9b04573>.

(34) Lingaiah Maram; Raghavendar Reddy Parigi; Das, B. Chiral Approach to Total Synthesis of Phytotoxic and Related Nonenolides: (Z)-Isomer of (6S,7R,9R)-6,7-Dihydroxy-9-Propylnon-4-Eno-9-Lactone, Herbarumin-III and Their C-9 Epimers. *Tetrahedron* **2016**, *72* (45), 7135–7142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tet.2016.09.052>.

(35) Seo, C.; Oh, H.; Lee, H. B.; Kim, J. K.; Kong, I. S.; Ahn, S. C. Hexaketides from Phytopathogenic Fungus *Paraphaeosphaeria Recurvifoliae*. *Bulletin of the Korean Chemical Society* **2007**, *28* (10), 1803–1806. <https://doi.org/10.5012/bkcs.2007.28.10.1803>.

(36) Cimmino, A.; Andolfi, A.; Fondevilla, S.; Abouzeid, M. A.; Rubiales, D.; Evidente, A. Pinolide, a New Nonenolide Produced by *Didymella Pinodes*, the Causal Agent of Ascochyta Blight on *Pisum Sativum*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* **2012**, *60* (21), 5273–5278. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf300824d>.

- (37) Srihari, P.; Maheswara Rao, G.; Srinivasa Rao, R.; Yadav, J. A Stereoselective Aldol Approach for the Total Synthesis of Herbarumin I and Stagonolide A. *Synthesis* **2010**, *2010* (14), 2407–2412. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0029-1218775>.
- (38) Selective Oxidations of Allylic and Benzylic Alcohols in the Presence of Saturated Alcohols. *Springer eBooks* **2006**, 289–330. https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-25725-x_8.
- (39) Günther Ohloff; Giersch, W. Conversion of Vicinal Diols into Dicarboxyl Compounds by Manganese Dioxide. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **1973**, *12* (5), 401–402. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.197304011>.
- (40) Fatemeh Zareh; Habib Firouzabadi; Gholinejad, M.; Sheibani, H. Barium Manganate: A Versatile Oxidant in Organic Synthesis. *Journal of the Iranian Chemical Society* **2023**, *20* (9), 2139–2161. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13738-023-02838-2>.
- (41) Wang, W.-X.; Zheng, M.-J.; Li, J.; Feng, T.; Li, Z.-H.; Huang, R.; Zheng, Y.-S.; Sun, H.; Ai, H.-L.; Liu, J.-K. Cytotoxic Polyketides from Endophytic Fungus *Phoma Bellidis* Harbored in *Tricyrtis Maculate*. *Phytochemistry Letters* **2018**, *29*, 41–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytol.2018.11.012>.
- (42) Davies, S. G.; Fletcher, A. M.; Thomson, J. E. Hydrogen Bond Directed Epoxidation: Diastereoselective Olefinic Oxidation of Allylic Alcohols and Amines. *Organic & Biomolecular Chemistry* **2014**, *12* (26), 4544. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ob00616j>.
- (43) Treadwell, E. M.; Yan, Z.; Xiao, X. Epoxidation with Possibilities: Discovering Stereochemistry in Organic Chemistry via Coupling Constants. *Journal of Chemical Education* **2017**, *94* (5), 640–643. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.6b00587>.
- (44) A. Evidente; Capasso, R.; Abouzeid, M. A.; Lanzetta, R.; M. Vurro; Bottalico, A. Three New Toxic Pinolidoxins from *Ascochyta Pinodes*. *Journal of Natural Products* **1993**, *56* (11), 1937–1943. <https://doi.org/10.1021/np50101a011>.
- (45) Ramalinga Uma; Christophe Crévisy; René Grée. Transposition of Allylic Alcohols into Carbonyl Compounds Mediated by Transition Metal Complexes. *Chemical Reviews* **2002**, *103* (1), 27–52. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr0103165>.
- (46) Oleg Yuzikhin; Mitina, G.; Berestetskiy, A. Herbicidal Potential of Stagonolide, a New Phytotoxic Nonenolide from *Stagonospora cirsii*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* **2007**, *55* (19), 7707–7711. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf070742c>.
- (47) Sadeghmoghaddam, E.; Gu, H.; Shon, Y.-S. Pd Nanoparticle-Catalyzed Isomerization vs Hydrogenation of Allyl Alcohol: Solvent-Dependent Regioselectivity. *ACS Catalysis* **2012**, *2* (9), 1838–1845. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cs300270d>.

- (48) Nanna Ahlsten; Bartoszewicz, A.; Belén Martín-Matute. Allylic Alcohols as Synthetic Enolate Equivalents: Isomerisation and Tandem Reactions Catalysed by Transition Metal Complexes. *Dalton Transactions* **2012**, 41 (6), 1660–1660. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c1dt11678a>.
- (49) Yadav, J. S.; Nanda, S.; Reddy, P. T.; Rao, A. B. Efficient Enantioselective Reduction of Ketones With *Daucus Carota* Root. *The Journal of Organic Chemistry* **2002**, 67 (11), 3900–3903. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jo010399p>.
- (50) Lacheretz, R.; Pardo, D. G.; Cossy, J. *Daucus Carota* Mediated-Reduction of Cyclic 3-Oxo-Amines. *Organic Letters* **2009**, 11 (6), 1245–1248. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ol8029214>.
- (51) Meshram, S. H.; Ramesh, T.; Nanubolu, J. B.; Srivastava, A. K.; Adari, B. R.; Sahu, N. Green Synthesis of Enantiopure Quinoxaline Alcohols Using *Daucus Carota*. *Chirality* **2019**, 31 (4), 312–320. <https://doi.org/10.1002/chir.23057>.
- (52) Acharya, C.; Mandal, M.; Dutta, T.; Ghosh, A. K.; Jaisankar, P. Enzyme from *Daucus Carota* Root Catalyzed Asymmetric Cross Aldol Reaction. *Tetrahedron Letters* **2016**, 57 (39), 4382–4385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tetlet.2016.08.056>.
- (53) Acharya, C.; Achari, A.; Jaisankar, P. *Daucus Carota* Root Enzyme Catalyzed Henry Reaction: A Green Approach. *Tetrahedron Letters* **2018**, 59 (7), 663–666. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tetlet.2018.01.009>.
- (54) Soria, A.; Sanz, M.; Villamiel, M. Determination of Minor Carbohydrates in Carrot (*Daucus Carota* L.) by GC–MS. *Food Chemistry* **2009**, 114 (2), 758–762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2008.10.060>.
- (55) Boadi, N. O.; Badu, M.; Kortei, N. K.; Saah, S. A.; Annor, B.; Mensah, M. B.; Okyere, H.; Fiebor, A. Nutritional Composition and Antioxidant Properties of Three Varieties of Carrot (*Daucus Carota*). *Scientific African* **2021**, 12, e00801. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2021.e00801>.
- (56) Sampada Chitale; Derasp, J. S.; Hussain, B.; Tanveer, K.; Beauchemin, A. M. Carbohydrates as Efficient Catalysts for the Hydration of α -Amino Nitriles. *Chemical Communications* **2016**, 52 (89), 13147–13150. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6cc07530d>.
- (57) Holton, R. A.; Kim, H. B.; Somoza, C.; Liang, F.; Biediger, R. J.; Boatman, P. D.; Shindo, M.; Smith, C. C.; Kim, S. First Total Synthesis of Taxol. 2. Completion of the c and D Rings. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **1994**, 116 (4), 1599–1600. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00083a067>.
- (58) Shi, M.; Society, R.; Al, E. *Chemistry of the Morita-Baylis-Hillman Reaction*; Cambridge Royal Society of Chemistry, 2011.
- (59) Kang, B.; Ikeda, K. 4-Dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP), a Superior Mediator for Morita–Balylis–Hillman Reaction-Triggered Annulative Condensation of Salicylaldehydes and Acrylonitrile to Form 3-

Cyano-2H-Chromenes. *Chemical and Pharmaceutical Bulletin* **2023**, *71* (4), 318–325. <https://doi.org/10.1248/cpb.c23-00068>.

(60) Drewes, S. E.; Njamela, O. L.; Emslie, N. D.; Ramesar, N.; Field, J. S. Intramolecular Baylis-Hillman Reaction: A Pathway to Substituted Coumarins. *Synthetic Communications* **1993**, *23* (20), 2807–2815. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00397919308012600>.

(61) Li, Q.; Kittiya Wongkhan; Luo, X.; Batsanov, A. S.; Judith; Lan, Y.; Wu, Y.; Marder, T. B.; Lei, A. A Novel Self-Promoted Morita-Baylis-Hillman-like Dimerization. *Chinese Science Bulletin* **2010**, *55* (25), 2794–2798. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11434-010-3270-9>.

(62) Jenner, G. Phosphine-Catalyzed Dimerization of Activated Alkenes under Ambient and High Pressure Conditions. *Tetrahedron Letters* **2000**, *41* (17), 3091–3094. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0040-4039\(00\)00346-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0040-4039(00)00346-4).

(63) Greve, H.; Schupp, P. J.; Ekaterina Eguereva; Kehraus, S.; Kelter, G.; Maier, A.; Fiebig, H.-H.; König, G. M. Apralactone a and a New Stereochemical Class of Curvularins from the Marine Fungus *Curvularia*Sp.. *European Journal of Organic Chemistry* **2008**, *2008* (30), 5085–5092. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejoc.200800522>.

(64) Asai, T.; Tsukada, K.; Ise, S.; Naoki Shirata; Hashimoto, M.; Fujii, I.; Katsuya Gomi; Kosuke Nakagawara; Kodama, E. N.; Oshima, Y. Use of a Biosynthetic Intermediate to Explore the Chemical Diversity of Pseudo-Natural Fungal Polyketides. *Nature Chemistry* **2015**, *7* (9), 737–743. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nchem.2308>.

(65) Matsui, H.; Morishita, Y.; Yamamoto, T.; Ozaki, T.; Sugawara, A.; Masumoto, Y.; Watanabe, M.; Watanabe, A.; Sato, H.; Kanazawa, J.; Taniguchi, T.; Uchiyama, M.; Asai, T. Discovery and Theoretical Studies of Nonenzymatic Polyketide Dimerizations of Chaetophenols. *Organic Letters* **2025**, *27* (5), 1095–1099. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.orglett.4c04346>.